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E-mail: islamjon86@gmail.com**BOSHLANG'ICH TAYYORGARLIK BOSQICHDA YOSH BOKSCHILARNING O'QUV
MASHG'ULOTLARINI REJALASHTIRISH**DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12599227>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichdagi yosh yosh bokschi­larning jismoniy tayyorgarlik mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirishga oid muammolar ularni va o'rganish jarayonida olingan natijalar va taxlili keltirilgan. Ushbu muammolarni hal etishda qo'llaniladigan "Boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi yosh bokschi­larning uchun o'quv-mashg'ulot dasturi" haqida kerakli ma'lumotlar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mashg'ulot dasturi, umumiy jismoniy tayyorgarlik, maxsus jismoniy tayyorgarlik, texnik tayyorgarlik, taktik tayyorgarlik, nazariy va psixologik tayyorgarlik

Mavzuning dolzarbligi. Dunyoda bolalar va o'smirlar sporti nazaryasi va amaliyotida yosh sportchilarni o'quv-mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirish, sportga saralash, jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish, psixologik, texnik-taktik hamda funksional tayyorgarligida qo'llaniladigan vosita va usullarni amaliyotga tadbiq etish borasida ko'plab imliy tadqiqot ishlari amalga oshirilgan. Jahonda sportchilarning sportdagi natijalari shiddat bilan o'sishi, ushbu sohada hozirgi kun talablariga mos o'quv mashg'ulotlarini tashkil­lash uchun eng qulay tizimini ishlab chiqish talabini qo'yimoqda.

Yosh bokschi­lar jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishda shug'ullanuvchilar yosh xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda mashg'ulotlarni zamon talablariga mos tarzda tashkillash bolalar va o'smirlar sporti nazaryasi va uslubiyotini rivojlantirish, respublika hamda xalqaro miqyosdagi dolzarb muammolardan biri sanaladi. [4.14-b] Yosh sportchilarning boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichda mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirishda ularning yoshga xos xususiyatlarini hisobga olish tayyorgarlikning keyingi bosqichlarida ham tayyorgarlikni barcha turlari (UJT, MJT, TT,) bo'yocha yuklamalarni optimal rejalashtirishga erishish mumkin [6. 34-b].

Boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi sportchilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishda qo'llaniladigan maxsus mashqlarni jismoniy sifatlarga, harakat

texnikasini rivojlantirishga mos tarzda qo'llash usullarini ishlab chiqish va amaliyotga tadbiq etish hozirda dolzarb masala hisoblanadi.[3. 24-b]

Tadqiqotning maqsadi. Yosh bokschi­lar mashg'ulotlarini optimal rejalashtirish asosida jismoniy tayyorgarligini oshirish.

Tadqiqot vazifalari. Yosh bokschi­lar amaliyotda mavjud rejalashtirish texnologiyalarini tadqiqotlar asosida o'rganish;

Yosh bokschi­lar mashg'ulotlarini rejalashtirishga ishlab chiqilgan dasturni nazariy jihatdan asoslash.

Tadqiqotni tashkil etilishi. Tadqiqot Namangan viloyati boks federatsiyaning 25 nafar malakali murabbiylari bilan anketa so'rovnomalari hamda intervyu-suhbat asosida tashkillandi. Murabbiylarning 65% 10 yildan ortiq tajribaga ega bo'lib ularning 4 nafari oliy toifali. Ushbu uyushtirilgan suhbatning asosiy maqsadi hozirda sport maktablarining boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi yosh qo'l jangichi bolalar mashg'ulot jarayoni tegishli hujjatlar hamda mashg'ulotda qo'llaniladigan vosita va usullarni haqida ma'lumot olish edi.

Bundan tashqari uchrashuvda qatnashgan trenirlardan hozirgi kunda mashg'ulot jarayonini eng muhim jihatlarini aniqlashga doir O'tkazilgan anketa so'rovnoma natijalari quyidagi 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

Boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi yosh qo'l jangichilarga o'quv mashg'ulotlarini olib boruvchi trenirlardan olingan anketa so'rovnoma natijalari

№	Savollar mazmuni	“ha” javobni berganlar soni	“yo‘q” javobini berganlar soni
1	Boks sport turiga oid adabiyotlar yetarlimi?	-	25
2	Mazkur bosqichda o'tkazilayotgan boks sport mashg'ulotni rejalashtirishda asos vazifasini bajaruvchi dasturi mavjudmi?		25
3	Mazkur bosqichdagi shug'ullanuvchi bolalar jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishda yoshga xos harakatli O'yinlar va maxsus mashqlardan foydalanasizmi?	12	13

Yuqoridagi keltirilgan anketa so'rovnomamizdagi savollar belgilab olgan vazifalarni aniqlashga qaratilgan bo'lib, undan olingan natijalarga asosan boshqa viloyatlarda ham ushbu sport turi bo'yicha o'tkazilib kelinayotgan mashg'ulotlardagi yuklamalar Bunga qo'shimcha sifatida Namangan viloyati Norin tumanidagi sport maktabidagi BTG 1 va 2-guruhda shug'ullanuvchi bolalarga berilayotgan yuklamalar hajmi va shiddatini aniqlash maqsadida "POLAR TIME"gi moslamadan foydalandik. Mazkur moslama orqali shu guruhdagi yosh boks sportchilarga berilayotgan yuklamalar hajmi va shiddatini shu yoshga mos hamda mos bo'lmagan jihatlarni aniqlandi.

Xulosa

1. Hozirda hayotimizni barcha jabhalari-da ilmiy izlanishlar va har bir amaliy ishlar o'zining me'yoriy asosiga ega bo'lishi zamon talabiga aylangan. Shu boisdan ham Respublikamizda faoliyat olib borayotgan barcha trenirlarni sohadagi etakchi olimlarning nazariy va amliy tajribalari bo'yicha ma'lumotlar bilan qurollantirish zarur.

2. Trenirlar yosh bokschilar uchun boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqishlarida mashg'ulotlar dasturi va undagi materiallarni uzviy ketma-ketlikda, yoshga xos bo'lgan mashqlarni to'g'ri belgilab tuzish malakasiga ega bo'lishlarini ta'minlashga lozim

3. Demak boshlang'ich tayyorgarlik bosqichidagi yosh bokschilarning jismoniy tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishga yillik mashg'ulot rejasi, vazifalari, uqulik tuzulishi, maxsus mashqlar va harakatli o'yinlar hamda tiklanish tadbirlarini rotsional rejalashtirish orqali erishilishini xulosa sifatida takidlash mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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